

Parents' Career Choice: Its Impact on the Career Path of Education Students

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Abstract:- The researchers study the impact of parents' influence on the career path of education students in the Philippine College of Science and Technology. The researchers focused on their data gathering using a survey questionnaire from Second Year to Fourth Year Education students at the Philippine College of Science and Technology. The study found out that "Criminology" was ranked as the first pre-degree program that education students preferred to enroll in. Data reveals that education students' Reason for Adhering to their Parents' Choice in a Career Path is they know that their parents want them to become professionals someday. The result was shown that The Impact of parents' choice on the career path of the respondents is that their children will find happiness and success in their career choice. For the recommendation Parents and students must communicate to make it possible for the parents to support and help their children as they pursue their desired degree programs. The choice of a career can affect a student's happiness and success in that field; thus, students must explain and inform their parents what they desire to pursue. Parents need to be aware that their choices regarding a child's career may have an impact on their choice in the future.

Keywords:- Career Path, Parents, Influence.

I. INTRODUCTION

Parents have a major influence on how their children develop their careers and make career decisions. Parents want their children to be successful and happy in life, and one thing that can affect that is their career decision-making. Making decisions regarding one's career is an important behavior that one engages in to establish his or her goals for a career. Students feel obligated to select a certain career or field of study, particularly during the transitioning period from high school to university or college. Due to a variety of factors, including the impact of peers, parents, family members, and role models, there will always be challenges throughout this period. Parental influence is the most common factor. Many parents are not aware of all the ways they can influence the career choices of their children.

A career can be described as a person's selection of roles they have taken on throughout the course of their lifetime. It is a person's desire through their employment, education, and

other aspects of life. In short, a career is the sum of all the work a person accomplishes during their lifetime. Because it is person-centered, it is extremely important to every person as they get ready for the future. Making a career decision is quite difficult, especially since life will depend on it. As a child grows up, the family and parents impact the student's future individuality. The role of preparing the child for education rests with the parents. Parents may become very concerned because choosing a career has an impact on a person's entire future.

Choosing a career is often regarded as a defining moment in the life of a young adult. This decision alone has the potential to either open or close the door to success. While it is commonly assumed that career decisions are made by individuals, research indicates that a variety of influences such as family, school, community, and social and economic factors are likely to influence one's final career decision (Ferry, 2006).

Education, financial incentives, peer pressure, and the influence of parents are sometimes utilized as pressure to push the students toward planned careers, regardless of their potential, genuine needs, and ego. (Alika, A. H., 2010). To make transparent decisions, however, learners also frequently turn to their parents, families, knowledgeable people, and peers and keep things clear in this regard.

A relational perspective approach makes it possible to comprehend career advancement easier. The key element of the career exploration process is the type of interactions and relationships that are developed between parents and children. It is possible for exploratory activities, job ambitions, future, and the perception of potential challenges in choosing a career to be influenced by the quality of parent-child connections, open communication, support provided, and trust.

This study is conducted because of the huge variety of instances that today's students and youths must tackle to understand how parents might influence their children's career choices. Parents must be involved to provide the children with the needed assistance and guidance to develop their interest and ability to use their hands and minds.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

Researchers explore the influence of parents' choices on the career path of education students of the Philippine College of Science and Technology for several key reasons: parents play a crucial role in shaping their children's aspirations and values, making it essential to understand how parental expectations impact career decisions in the field of education.

This research also delves into the long-term consequences of job satisfaction and diversity in education. Additionally, it seeks to understand the psychological well-being of students and the alignment between their aspirations and familial choices. Ultimately, shedding light on the intricate interplay of influences in career decision-making in the education sector.

A. Parents as the key factor.

Particularly, parents and family members play a key part in determining a person's preferred career. Interpersonal influence and role influences from models and close relationships are some aspects that people often consider while choosing a career or vocation. The benefits of parents becoming more actively involved in their kids' education achieving results (Wikelund, 2006). Parental support and guidance were found to be positively connected to professional decision-making self-efficacy and career-planning behavior among teenagers in a 2020 study that was published in the Journal of Adolescence. However, the study also discovered that these results were inversely correlated with parental control and pressure. Parental support was positively correlated with career decision-making self-efficacy (i.e., the belief in one's capacity to make effective career decisions), which in turn was positively correlated with career exploration behavior, according to a 2017 study published in the Journal of Career Assessment.

According to a 2019 study that was published in the Journal of Career Development, parental influence was among the most important determinants of college students' self-efficacy in selecting career decisions. The study also discovered a positive relationship between parental influence and career exploration behavior. According to a 2014 study that appeared in the Journal of Vocational Behavior, parents can have both good and negative effects on their kids' professional decisions. Parental encouragement and support were linked to more adaptable career decision-making, while parental pressure and control were linked to less adaptable career decision-making.

However, choosing a career is difficult, especially in these uncertain economic times, making it even more difficult for students to choose a path (William, 2016). Wattles (as cited by Edwards and Quinter, 2011) also claims that, with the advancement of information technology over the years, choosing a career "has become a complex science."

For example, it was common in the early days for children to follow in their parent's footsteps or occupation; for example, if one is the son of a blacksmith, he should become a blacksmith when he reaches the appropriate age. Nowadays, however, an individual can pursue his or her life ambitions and become a successful or wealthy person if he or she has the necessary skills.

B. Interrelationships between career choice, peer group, and parental influence

There has recently been an increase in interest in the interrelationships between career choice, peer group, and parental influence. More importantly, the focus has been on the factors that influence an individual's decision to pursue a career. Parents have always been fascinated by their children's achievements as they grow up. The young adolescent in school is expected to set high goals for himself or herself and work hard to achieve those goals. Furthermore, children are made aware of the prestige that comes with a successful career choice. The glory associated with certain careers is frequently an illusion. Empirical findings have confirmed, to a greater extent, the impact of a person's family and family goals and objectives on his or her career choice. According to Trost and Levin (2000), a child's behavior or character is influenced by his or her family. Tella (2003) discovered that parents play an important role in laying the groundwork for their children's careers.

According to the findings of Parola and Marcionetti (2021), young people who have had parental support are more likely to pursue a career and are more satisfied with their lives. Parents want their children to be happy and successful, so they provide information, motivation, and guidance in their career choices. Most people choose a profession because they have a long history with it.

III. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

The descriptive developmental method of research was used in the study. It was descriptive because the main purpose of the study was to determine The Impact of Parents' Choices on the Career Path of Selected Education Students of the Philippine College of Science and Technology. Relevant data were systematically recorded, analyzed, and interpreted to have a clear description of the prevailing condition. The researchers carefully followed the ordered sequence of the research technique to guarantee objectivity and completeness in obtaining all the initial and necessary information to deal with research problems. The sequential order was stated in the prior discussion. Instrumental/ Source of Data.

A. Pre-degree program

The primary source of data used by the researchers was the survey questionnaires and the data to be gathered will be used to know the impact on the career path of education students. This questionnaire, which was the main data gathering tool in this study was personally prepared by

Program	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Rank
Criminology	13	23.64%	1
Engineering	6	10.91%	5
Maritime Studies	2	3.64%	7.5
Accountancy	8	14.55%	3
Tourism Management	12	21.82%	2
Hotel Management	5	9.09%	6
Computer Studies	2	3.64%	7.5
Business Administration	7	12.73%	4

researchers often carefully studying the checklist item, and was properly validated as to its face and content of experts in the test and questionnaire.

Table 1 There is pre- degree program that they prefer to enroll

B. Primary reasons why education students adhered to their parents' choice of degree program.

Table 2 shows the primary reasons why education students adhered to their parents' choice of degree program. The item on this part of the questionnaire features the reason for adhering to parents' choice in choosing a career path. (1)

Table 2 Primary reasons why education students adhered to their parents' choice of degree program.

Reason for Adhering Parents' Choice in Choosing a Career Path	HI 5	VI 4	MI 3	NI 2	LI 1	Average Weighted Mean	Description
This is the financial capability of my parents	18	16	9	7	5	3.64	Very Influential
This is the profession of my parents.	14	7	7	7	20	2.78	Moderately Influential
My parents want me to become a professional someday.	39	17	4	1	0	5.04	Highly Influential
I want to make my parents proud.	34	15	5	0	1	4.47	Highly Influential
My parents always choose what I'll do in school.	12	17	10	6	10	3.27	Moderately Influential
As growing up, my parents expected me to follow their instructions regarding my behavior and decisions.	10	17	15	7	6	3.33	Moderately Influential
Overall Average Weighted Mean						3.76	

C. Impact of Parents on the Students' Career Path

Table 3 shows the impact of parents in to the students career path such as; (1) Parents help students to gain an understanding of the field of choice through direct, frequent, and early exposure to the profession with the weighted means of 3.47, (2) Students develop an understanding of the duties, responsibilities and lifestyles of the of the choice profession with the weighted means of 3.64, (3) Parents want their

“This is the financial capability of my parents” with a weighted means of 3.64, (2) “This is the profession of my parents” with a weighted means of 2.78, (3) “My parents want me to become professional someday” with a weighted means of 5.04, (4) “I want to make my parents proud” with a weighted means of 4.47, (5) “My parents always choose what I'll do in school” with a weighted means of 3.27, (6) “As growing up, my parents expected me to follow their instructions regarding my behavior and decisions” with a weighted means of 3.33.

Based on the data presented in Table 2, there are two students highly influential “My parents want me to become professional someday” and “I want to make my parents proud”. And the student’s very influence is “This is the financial capability of my parents”. And the student's Moderately Influential is “This is the profession of my parents”, “My parents always choose what I'll do in school” and “As growing up, my parents expected me to follow their instructions regarding my behavior and decision”. The overall result of the survey implies that many of the respondents’ parents want them to become professionals someday and want to make their parents proud.

The overall result of the survey as shown by the overall weighted mean of 3.76 shows that the respondents are very influential.

children to find happiness and success in career choice with the weighted means of 3.94, (4) Parents influence their children to aim at high academic qualifications for a successful with the weighted means of 3.89, (5) Family engagement in schools improves student achievement with the weighted means of 3.58, (6) Parental involvement in career decision making pressure students to achieve a career status beyond their talents with the weighted means of 3.31, (7)

Parents think that they should choose their children's career but that will only lead the child to be unhappy profession with the weighted means of 3.33, (8) The students' education is becoming increasingly dependent upon what parents want their children to achieve rather than on the student's abilities and effort with the weighted means of 3.31, (9) Students view pressure from parents negatively and instead of succeeding they fail in achieving high performance in school with the weighted means of 3.16, and (10) My parents' involvement in my academics reinforce my academic performance with the weighted means of 3.15 .

Based on the data presented in table 3, students are moderately aware are “Parents want their children to find happiness and success in career choice”, “Parents influence their children to aim at high academic qualifications for a successful career”, “Students develop an understanding of the duties, responsibilities, and lifestyles of the choice profession”, “Family engagement in schools improves student

achievement”, and “Parents help students to gain an understanding of the field of choice through direct, frequent, and early exposure to the profession”. And students somewhat aware are “Parents think that they should choose their children's career but that will only lead the child to be unhappy”, “Parental involvement in career decision making pressure students to achieve a career status beyond their talents”, “The student's education is becoming increasingly dependent upon what parents want their children to achieve rather than on the student's abilities and efforts”, “Students view pressure from parents negatively and instead of succeeding they fail in achieving high performance in school”, and “My parents' involvement in my academics reinforce my academic performance”.

The overall result of the survey as shown by the overall weighted mean of 3.48 shows that the respondents are moderately aware.

Table 3 Impact of Parents to the students Career Path

Impact	EA 5	MA 4	SWA 3	SA 2	NA 1	Average Weighted Mean	Description
1. Parents help students to gain an understanding of the field of choice through direct, frequent, and early exposure to the Profession.	13	16	13	10	3	3.47	Moderately Aware
2. Students develop an understanding of the duties, responsibilities and lifestyles of the of the choice profession.	11	24	11	7	2	3.64	Moderately Aware
3. Parents want their children to find happiness and success in career choice.	23	14	12	3	3	3.93	Moderately Aware
4. Parents influence their children to aim at high academic qualifications for a successful career.	25	14	7	4	4	3.89	Moderately Aware
5. Family engagement in schools improves student achievement.	17	15	12	5	6	3.58	Moderately Aware
6. Parental involvement in career decision making pressure students to achieve a career status beyond their talents.	12	15	13	8	7	3.31	Somewhat Aware
7. Parents think that they should choose their children's career but that will only lead the child to be unhappy.	11	14	20	2	8	3.33	Somewhat Aware
8. The students' education is becoming increasingly dependent upon what parents want their children to achieve rather than on the student's abilities and efforts.	8	17	20	4	6	3.31	Somewhat Aware
9. Students view pressure from parents negatively and instead of succeeding they fail in achieving high performance in school.	12	14	10	8	12	3.16	Somewhat Aware
10. My parents' involvement in my academics reinforce my academic performance.	9	12	19	8	7	3.15	Somewhat Aware
Overall Average Weighted Mean						3.48	

IV. CONCLUSIONS

After a careful examination of the study, the researchers made the following conclusions: Based on the data gathered for SOP 1 “Criminology” was ranked as the first-pre-degree program that education students preferred to enroll in. Based on the data gathered for SOP 2- The Reason for Adhering to Parents' Choice in Choosing a Career Path is they know that their “parents want them to become professional someday”. Based on the data gathered for SOP 3 – The Impact of parent’s choice on the career path of the respondents is that their children will find happiness and success in their career choice.

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